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NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF VALUE IN TEACHER EDUCATION

Research paper in EDUCATION

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Abstract:

In the present time Computer Education, Management Education, Education for Peace, Environmental Education and Adolescent Education have gained prominent place in education. The concept of Value Education is such that Value Education is very much required in the present social life; Value Education contributes in individual's life and through it moral development of society could be enhanced.

A tree becomes meaningful or successful when it becomes full with fruits and flowers. In the same way, human life is like tree. In the same way, the life of human being becomes meaningful when different virtues like service, humility, patience, kindness and holiness become integral part of his or her life and till all these virtues don't become part and parcel of the life individual's life cannot become Complete Life or Divine Life. The main objective of education is to enrich human life with Completeness and Divinity. Such practices are not seen in the present education system. Therefore, it is the demand of present time that we should find a new direction or a way so that human being can be made Human Being in real sense. Value education is not the subject that can be taught but it is the subject to put into practice. Its direct and indirect effects can be seen in the society. To establish values, it is necessary to plan lessons by referring to the values inherent in the lessons of the subject. In our textbooks, there is rich treasure of values. It is necessary to discuss the lesson with the help of values that are inherent in the lessons while

conducting teaching practices in the classrooms and as a result values can be inculcated in the lives of the students and with the help of these values different skills can be developed in the lives of the students.

The environment in the schools should be such that moral values can be cultivated among the students since the cultivation of values is taking place in the nearby environment and social conditions.

Keywords: *Education, Value General decline & deterioration of morality, weaken social and moral values in new generation, moral values has to be organized in the institutions, teachers role, values and Qualities of behavior, grooming the teacher, sustaining teachers motivation.*

1. Introduction

To cultivate the values among the students it is necessary to teach value based lessons while conducting teaching practices inside and outside the classrooms. To motivate the students who show honest should be appreciated by giving their examples to other students by giving examples of their honesty during different occasions and incidents that take place in home or outside the home so that environment in the school can be created from which other students can be motivated.

To teach the value of honesty different activities like historical characters, life events of great people, moral stories and sports can be arranged in the schools and value education can be imparted to the students.

2. Need of Value of Honesty

In today's world there is an environment of danger, unfaithfulness and doubt. One country is afraid of another country; different countries increase their military power so that other countries may not attack them. In such environment of doubt and danger both the countries remain engaged in the preparation of war which ultimately results into war. In the present time much increase of information can be witnessed. The constant flow of the information from all the direction is continuously flowing. It is the task of Value Education to validate all the information. In the present education system, there is an ardent need of education of value of honesty. Mother Teresa has said, "For the value of honesty, disseminate love wherever you go. Begin from home. Give love to your children, your life partner and your neighbors". A person should become happier and cordial after he or she meets you. You should be transmitter of love

and kindness that have enshrined by God. There should be wholeheartedness and kindness on your face, in your eyes, smile and greetings.

3 Teachers for the Inculcation of Value of Honesty

Nobody can build and cultivate the character of the students as easily as their teachers, be it the parents of the students or the social national leaders. The impact of teachers on the students is greater than the impact of their own parents or guardians. It may be possible that a son or a daughter may not believe or obey what his or her ward advice or orders but a student certainly has faith in his or her teacher. The teacher should take benefit of the faith of his or her students over him or her for student's individual development and for the development of Nation. The teacher can add everyday mannerism and values while he or she teaches any subjects in the classroom. The teacher can cultivate among the students higher feelings for their subjects and cultivate their positive attitudes. Thus, if the teachers practice their teaching in such a way than cultivation of the students character can be accomplished with the help of all the subjects including Numbers to Poetry.”

The teacher should become live book. The teacher should do much reading of the chapters from the voluminous books and should narrate the incidents among the students in the form of story, memory, or the example. The teacher can teach the value of honesty by conducting following activities in schools:

3.1 Poetry Recitation Function

For the mental development of the students and to develop positive mannerism among the students Poetry Recitation Function or Group Recitation of Poetry may prove very useful. The emotions of the poetry leave the impact indirectly on the mind and heart of the listener. There is magical impact of blessed and virtuous music in the life of an individual through which mental development and character development of an individual can take place.

3.2 Antashari Function

Antashari also proves to be effective for the development of interest and character among the students. It helps to increase the memory of the students with entertainment. They remember and recite different forms of poetry which helps them to develop research intelligence among them.

3.3 Eloquence Competition

Eloquence competition is not to promote discussion that may lead to any adverse situation but it is to cultivate values and to make choice of the subject on which healthy debate can be organized. For example in such subjects, truth, patience, honesty, selflessness, hard work, national commitment, humility, cooperation etc. virtues may take place. All the students should be motivated to speak about the virtues of any subject.

3.4 One Act Play

One Act Play also proves to be very effective for the development of character. For national development and integration, plays which as are full of virtues and character of vigor and virtue should be enacted instead of comic and satirical plays. All the preparation of the play should be accomplished by the students themselves. The main objective should be to make the students artists but through the medium of this art he should be made studious and virtuous. A student should become self-transformer instead of an actor.

3.5 Celebration of Festivals and Birth Ceremonies

To search innovative thoughts it is necessary to organize celebration of festivals and birth ceremonies of the great people. It is also important to organize national days and festivals for the development of values among the students. The students can be motivated by narrating among them the life span of the great people, virtuous thoughts of life and the great work done by the great people. Each day of the life is pious. One should live his or her life with virtue, happiness and being useful to others. Thus, moral commitment can be cultivate among the students without any doubt.

4. Conclusion

When the teachers become committed to implement and practice all the values in their own lives, than they can become role model for their students. Until the teachers become adapted to the values, they would not be able to become committed for their roles and responsibilities. And therefore they should become pious through which the students become self-motivated to lead pious life.

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